

THE PHENOMENON MIRATIVITY IN LINGUISTICS

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<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10837622>

Abstract. *The goal of this paper is to go back the basics and examine mirativity from the point of view of a field linguistics and how the speaker of a language linguistically expresses her surprise.*

Keywords: *Surprise, unexpectedness, counterexpectation, unprepared mind, new information, discovery, admiring, DeLancey.*

The phenomenon mirativity is broadly defined as the linguistic expression of surprise and related concepts such as unexpectedness and new information. There are many excellent descriptions of mirativity in various language grammars, and more recently there has been a flurry of research refining mirativity to include how languages linguistically realize surprise and related concepts such as “unexpectedness” and “new information”. It can be argued that treating mirativity as surprise is an overly simplistic approach; as such, many researchers have shown that mirativity encompasses many more nuanced or specialized meanings, such as, for example, the linguistic response to “new information”, or to an event that is “out of control”. In English language one can give a multitude of linguistic options for showing the surprise of the speaker:

“You made it!”

“ I do not believe you made it!”

“Looks like you made it!”

“Wow, you are here!”

“I’m amazed you made it!”

“That can’t be who I think it is!”

“What a surprise!”...etc.

DeLancey also describes mirative meaning in psychological and cognitive terms: “Mirativity marks both statements based on inference and statements based on direct experience for which the speaker had no psychological preparation...(DeLancey 1997:35-36).

In more recent work, Aikhenvald’s (2012, 437) studies define the various descriptions of mirativity into five major subtypes of meaning:

- 1) Sudden discovery
- 2) Surprise of the speaker
- 3) Unprepared mind
- 4) Counterexpectation
- 5) Information new to the speaker

Other languages have mirative morphemes that seem to fall somewhere in between. English word *wow* is typically used to express a speaker’s surprise, as in the unexpected arrival of a colleague at a meeting in: “Wow, you made it!”.

In addition, markers of evidentiality inference and hearsay are often used as miratives, expressing surprise (DeLancey 1997, 2001). The Turkish morpheme “-*mish*” cannot only express the meaning of perfect aspect but also the evidential meanings of inference and hearsay, as well as mirativity (Slobin&Aksu 1982: 187 (3)):

Aliya kelmish.

Aliya has come.

Aliya came.

a) Inference: the speaker sees Aliya’s coat hanging in the front hall, but has not yet seen Aliya.

b) Hearsay: the speaker has been told that Aliya has arrived, but has not yet seen Aliya.

c) Surprise: the speaker hears someone approach, opens the door, and sees Aliya- a totally unexpected visitor. (Slobin&Aksu 1982: 187)

Evidential markers may gain additional meanings and extensions such as the probability of an event or the reliability of information (often called ‘epistemic’ meanings), or unusual and ‘surprising’ information (called ‘mirative’ in the recent literature, following DeLancey’s 1997). Mirative extensions have been noticed for most systems – we find examples in Jarawara, Yukaghir, Abkhaz as well as in Turkic. The inferential forms may be employed to focus the listener’s attention on crucial points in a narrative, as in Abkhaz; this is comparable to the adversative (‘but’) and argumentative values of evidentials in Western Armenian as illustrated by Donabédian 2000).

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